

Reviewer 2:

Thank you for the constructive feedback. Following are our responses to the points mentioned in the review.

1. We have provided strong reasons and results for almost every idea we have presented in the paper. The reasons for equations 1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 10, 11 are presented very clearly. We feel we have provided enough reasons for using the `instant_score` and `score` functions (equations 3, 8, 9) as well, however if unclear we can present it in more detail. We need to improve the Coefficient Of Variation (Table 4) and still ensure no server shoots or diminishes its timeout which can result in the elections running forever. Thus, we need to meet the domain and range restrictions that we described in Table 2 and reasoned with the paragraph below equation 4. To suit these requirements we used the functions mentioned (figures 2, 4). For `instant_score`, $\cos(x)$ itself does not suffice the conditions in Table 2 and it's a strictly decreasing function in our domain. To correct the monotonicity and balance curve's slope for better Coefficient Of Variation we multiply the arctan component. These two components do not provide the Coefficient Of Variation in our required range owing to its small slope. To improve this, we multiply $\sqrt{2}$. Finally, to satisfy the last condition in Table 2, we add one. The other score functions are constructed similarly. We nowhere claim that the score functions we use are the best, however due to the reasons provided and the results achieved it proficiently suits our needs. Finding the theoretically optimal score functions can be a research topic in itself and fellow researchers are invited to pursue it. Moreover, if needed we can definitely add these details in our camera-ready version.
2. The number of RPC calls in the system is still linear in terms of number of servers, same as vanilla Raft algorithm. So, our algorithm has the same asymptotic time complexity as vanilla raft, i.e., $O(\text{Number_Of_Servers})$.
3. Refer to Point 5.
4. We show experiments with 20 initial servers and disconnecting 8 servers, similar to what have been done in previous research, which have already been cited. We have also ran experiments with other configurations where our algorithm achieves similar election efficiency improvements, but we believe that showing all this data in the paper might be redundant. Still if the reviewers suggest then we can include results for other configurations as well in the camera-ready version.
5. We define an iteration as: Take 20 initial servers and disconnect 8 one-by-one. We run 200 such iterations and show the average number of terms after each server is disconnected, similar to the concept in the Raft paper. Let's define a trial as: Running these 200 iterations. When the number of iterations are 200 and above, the average number of terms remain consistent across different trials. However, with a lower number of iterations we get varying results across different trails. We have shared the tables showing results across 5 trials with 10, 50 and 200 iterations, below. We calculate the standard deviation and the difference between the maximum and minimum values across the five trials for each server disconnect from the table. We observe a significant improvement in these values as the number of iterations increases. This suggests that with an increasing number of iterations, we get more consistent results. Since the results are fairly sufficient and consistent with 200 iterations and there is no significant change after that, we use this value.

	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5	Standard Deviation	Max Difference
Server 1	2.9	2.4	4.1	4.2	2.6	0.761	1.8
Server 2	5.4	5.1	6.2	6.6	4.7	0.701	1.9
Server 3	7	6.5	8	8.6	6.1	0.931	2.5
Server 4	9	8.3	10.2	9.7	7.7	0.906	2.5
Server 5	10.5	10	12	11.8	9.4	1.011	2.6
Server 6	12.9	12.5	14.1	13	11.3	0.902	2.8
Server 7	16.5	14.7	17.1	15.7	14.3	1.054	2.8
Server 8	19.1	18.2	18.9	19.5	16.7	0.985	2.8

10 Iterations

	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5	Standard Deviation	Max Difference
Server 1	3.4	2.88	3.2	3.12	3.36	0.187	0.52
Server 2	5.58	5.56	5.56	5.44	5.92	0.162	0.48
Server 3	8.3	8.06	7.7	7.64	8.08	0.249	0.66
Server 4	9.88	10.06	9.6	9.54	9.94	0.201	0.52
Server 5	11.98	12.02	11.74	11.4	12.14	0.262	0.74
Server 6	14.34	14.08	13.86	13.3	14.36	0.390	1.06
Server 7	17.2	17.62	16.9	15.72	17.16	0.643	1.9
Server 8	19.68	20.5	19.48	18.46	20	0.676	2.04

50 Iterations

	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Trial 4	Trial 5	Standard Deviation	Maximum Difference
Server 1	3.31	3.16	3.15	3.25	3.1	0.076	0.21
Server 2	5.91	5.71	5.66	5.81	5.65	0.099	0.26
Server 3	8.26	8.07	8.04	8.21	8.05	0.091	0.22
Server 4	9.92	9.81	9.83	9.89	9.82	0.043	0.11
Server 5	11.74	11.68	11.67	11.73	11.7	0.027	0.07
Server 6	13.99	13.8	13.74	13.93	13.78	0.095	0.25
Server 7	16.43	16.51	16.48	16.52	16.51	0.033	0.09
Server 8	19.32	19.23	19.22	19.34	19.22	0.053	0.12

200 Iterations

- The timeout for every server is given by [timeout = base + RTO]. For each equation that we present to update any $RTO_{\{C/S/L\}}$, we mean to update the RTO value in the timeout, with immediate effect. We can change the naming conventions in camera-ready versions for better clarity on this.
- Sure, we will take a note on this and rewrite it if it is unclear currently. We chose only candidates in the leader group, these servers became candidates as they timed out earlier than others, in previous elections. By removing the base value from these timeouts (and thus, only RTO remains) we make them even more likely to timeout and start election earlier.

8. For the second phase we test with the values, 5,10,15,20,25,30,35,40,45,50. There aren't significant improvements observed in election efficiency after 30, and we want to avoid a very time-consuming booting process therefore,we choose the value=30. If the reviewers suggest we can add data for this in the paper as well.
9. We feel we have provided sufficient validations for this statement in results as well. Figures 7 and 8 would have term-values incrementing by one sequentially in the last row had we eradicated split-votes. Table5 and figures 7 and 8 show election-success-rate has improved significantly. We nowhere claim our approach leads to optimal split-votes scenarios, but we reduce them significantly.
10. Refer to Point 1.

We feel we have addressed all the weaknesses with sufficient data. With what we have presented in the paper and in our responses above, we hope we have addressed your concerns sufficiently and any upgrades to our score will be really helpful.